

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

Volume I Issue VII

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

NOVEMBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Volume I Issue VII

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VII (November 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

JERRICK T. PARIAN, EdD

Instructor III

Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology - Main Campus

Bunawan, Agusan del Sur, Caraga, Philippines

[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17533609](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17533609)

Bread or Winner?

Society says a breadwinner is one who strives harder,
It refers to an older brother, a dreaming sister or a youngest member.
They called as "winner" when success burns brighter,
But they are "bread" to silence the family's hugger.

If winners take it all, then why do they suffer?
Carrying bills, tuition, and needs that never falter.
Their dreams grow quiet, while responsibilities scream louder,
Yet they smile despite of pain because family's love is stronger.

They whisper to the stars, "Will this ever be over?"
Opportunities fade, patience breaks but still, they shoulder.
Hoping the heavens hear what words can't utter,
To never give up, though the weight grows heavier.

Many breadwinners live like unsolved figures,
Tracing their worth through endless numbers.
Wishing for a guide, a voice or a mentor,
To say, "You are more than bread, you are the winner."